

Bidirectional Hybrid Optical Wireless Communication System for Indoor Networks

Syed Samiullah Taran^{1*}

¹Department of Physics, University of Balochistan, Quetta, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Optical band of electromagnetic spectrum is classified into three portions i.e., infrared, visible and ultraviolet lights. Using visible light for downlink transmission is strongly appreciated because it provides communication along with illumination. But for uplink, visible light is avoided as it is uncomfortable for eyes and due to energy limitation of portable devices. Instead of visible light, infrared light is more attractive for uplink if used according to eye and skin safety standards. This paper takes into consideration a bidirectional hybrid OWC system for indoor networks which consists of VLC for downlink and IRWC for uplink. For both transmitters (LED send IRED), transconductance circuits with feedback topology are used. On receiving side, same op-amp based circuit with PD BPW34 is used for both VLC and IRWC. The commercially available USB to TTL converters is employed on both sides as processing units. The experimental setup is used to examine the SER with respect to separation between transmitter and receiver for different BR. According to results, The SER increases, and CRS decreases with increasing separation at same BR or with increasing BR at same separation. the best SER vs distance range were obtained at BR 1200 and below 1200 for VLC and IRWC.

INTRODUCTION

Optical wireless communication OWC is classified as visible light communication (VLC) and infrared wireless communication (IRWC). In VLC, high brightness LED (HB-LED) for illumination along with data transmission is employed [1]. The LEDs are transmitter of VLC. The signals are received by photodiode. On receiving side, intensity modulation (IM) and direct detection (DD) is done. LED can switch high-speed rate. [2]. Another shortrange medium for indoor wireless communication is IRWC. IR spectra is followed by visible light. IR and visible light both

have extremely similar characteristics, like dark colored objects can absorb the rays of light (infrared and visible light), objects having light color reflects light diffusely and these rays can be reflected directionally by shiny surfaces. Both kinds of lights can pass through penetrate opaque barriers [3]. Most of the existing research work on VLC focuses, particularly on the downlink. But the illumination is not required in portable devices for uplink due to energy limitation and can be uncomfortable for human eyes during working. Due to these reasons, VLC is strongly accepted for downlink implementation within a local network instead of

Corresponding author. Syed Samiullah Taran*

E-mail address: ssamiullah874@gmail.com

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uplink. However, complementing VLC with another uplink technology, which avoids issues related to uplink VLC system. Then IRWC is better choice. IRWC also have ability to provide high transmission speed as well as security application. IRWC system possesses similar benefits as that of VLC system. The IRWC is also favorable due to extra advantages over VLC, like IR system do not have dimming issue. Using safety precaution related to IR rays, it is not problematic for human eye as VLC [4]. In a bidirectional OWC system, IR for uplink have no interference with downlink visible light [5]. IR provides nearly similar data rate as that of VLC. IRWC can attain data rate up to 10 Gb/s using simple on-off key (OOK) modulation [4]. The current VLC based system work with high illumination. For low LED illumination level in case of day light and at night. The system is not designed. On other hand, IR based OWC can be a choice for low illumination levels which needs an investigation. Efforts are needed to construct a bidirectional reliable OWC hybrid system based on IRED and LEDs.

METHODOLOGY

A. Circuit Analysis of Transmitter Circuits

There is a nonlinear relation between intensity of transmitted signals and forward voltage of IRED and LED. By applying voltage modulation directly to IRED and LED can produce distortion in the transmitted signals [6] [7]. On the other hand, the driving current for IRED and LED is proportional to the intensity of optical signal. In other words, input current and intensity have linear relation with each other [6] [8]. To solve the issue of linearity between input voltage and output intensity. A voltage to current converting setup is needed to achieve suitable current for IRED and LED. Such task can be performed by BJT based transconductance circuit with feedback topology. The BJT based transconductance circuit with feedback topology is shown in Fig 1.

Fig.1. the BJT transconductance circuit with feedback topology Equations (12) and (2) can be used to find the values of (R_e) and (R_b) for transimpedance circuit with feedback [8]. These circuit analyses will be used for LED and IRED.

$$R_e = \frac{\frac{1}{3}V_{cc} - V_{be}}{i_{LED,max}} \quad (1)$$

and

$$R_b = (\beta_{max} + 1) \left(\frac{V_{in} - V_{be}}{i_{LED,max}} - R_e \right) \quad (2)$$

B. For VLC transmitter (LED)

The LED of 20mA was employed for VLC. This LED was connected in transconductance circuit with feedback, in which the BJT- based transistor BC-547 was used, whose β_{max} at 20mA current is 120 according to datasheet. For $V_{cc} = 5V$, $V_{be} = 0.7V$, $\beta_{max} = 120$ and $i_{LED,max} = 20mA$, the value of $R_{e,(LED)}$ and $R_{b,(LED)}$ was calculated from above equations (1) and (2). The calculated value of $R_{e,(LED)}$ is 48.33Ω and the closest practical value of $R_{e,(LED)}$ is 33Ω . And the value of $R_{b,(LED)}$ is 20167.07Ω and the closest practical value of $R_{b,(LED)}$ is 20000.00Ω i.e., $20K\Omega$. The value of current measured by multimeter is 20.2 mA near to selected value of current 20 mA is shown in Fig. 2(a).

Fig. 2. (a) The value of current measured by multimeter is 20.2 mA near to selected value of current 20 mA. (b) The value of current measured by multimeter is 94.2 mA near to selected value of current 100 mA. C. For IRWC Transmitter (IRED). Again, the same BJT-based transconductance circuit with feedback was used, in which same transistor BC547 and IRED were connected. To evaluate the values of $R_{e,(IRED)}$ and $R_{b,(IRED)}$ for selected IRED, again using the (1) and (2) equations. for $R_{e,(IRED)}$ $V_{cc} = 5V$, $V_{be} = 0.7V$, $\beta_{max} = 120$ and $i_{LED,max} = 100mA$. Substituting these values in (1) and (2) equation. The $R_{e,(IRED)}$ is 9.6Ω and the closest practical value of $R_{e,(IRED)}$ is 10Ω . And The $R_{b,(IRED)}$ is 3993Ω and the closest practical value of $R_{b,(IRED)}$ is 3900Ω i.e., $3.9K\Omega$. The value of current measured by multimeter is 94.2 mA near to selected value of current 100 mA is shown in Fig. 2(b).

D. Receiver for Visible And Infrared Transmitter

On reception side, same circuit and photodiode is proposed for receiving both IR and visible light signals. The circuit is shown in Fig 3. The BPW34 photodiode (PD) is used in the receiving circuit due to its advantages like, fast switching, have response for both visible and infrared light etc. the op-amp LM-318 is selected as it can work with high speed. The resistor is $470K\Omega$ connected to input supply of 5V and the supply for op-amp is $+V_{cc} = +5V$ and $-V_{cc} = -5V$.

Fig. 3. The circuit diagram for receiving circuit of visible and infrared lights.

E. Implementation of Bidirectional Transmission System

The setup consists of two laptops, two PL2303 USB to TTL-converter which were the processing units for transmitters (IRED and LED) and receivers (photodiodes), receiver circuits for visible light and infrared light, and transmitter circuit for Led and IRED. The maximum baud rate at which this device can transmit and receive data bidirectionally by using direct wired connection between Tx and Rx, is 10MB. One PL2303 USB to TTL-converter is connected to 1st laptop. One receiver circuit for receiving infrared signals and one transmitter circuit for LED to transmit visible light signal are connected to 1st laptop through processing unit PL2303 USB to TTL-converter. Similarly, the 2nd PL2303 USB to TTL-converter is connected to 2nd laptop. 2nd receiver circuit for receiving visible light signals and 2nd transmitter circuit for IRED to transmit IR signal are connected to 2nd laptop through processing unit PL2303 USB to TTL-converter. The signals were transmitted and received bidirectionally on each laptop simultaneously through serial monitor cool term software. The screen shot of cool term software is shown in Fig 4. The block diagram of bi direction transmission system is shown in Fig 5.

Fig. 4. The screen shot of cool term software

F. Determination of Correctly Received Symbols (CRS) And Symbol Error Rate (SER)

The CRS were determined for different baud rates (BR) and separation. The transmitted symbols (S_T) for each BR and separation, were 1000. Finally, all results of CRS were converted into SER by using formula

$$S_{SER} = \frac{S_T - S_R}{S_T} \quad (3)$$

Here, S_{SER} = Symbol error rate S_R = Correctly Received Symbols [9]. When the value of CRS increases then the SER will decrease and vice versa.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results For VLC

The range of separation between LED and PD was from 0.0cm to 17.6cm. The range of the BR for VLC was between 1200 and 115200. By increasing the BR, the range of separation with zero SER were decreasing. For 115200 BR, the SER was one in the entire range of separation, while at the 1200 BR, SER was zero in the entire range of separation. All the discussed results for SER vs Distane for VLC can be seen in graph shown in figures 6.

Fig 6. SER vs Distance graph for VLC for baud rates between 1200 to 115200.

B. Results For IRWC

The range of separation between IRED and PD was from 0.0cm to 20.7cm. The range of the BR for IRWC was between 600 and 57600. By increasing the BR, the range of

separation with zero SER were decreasing. For 57600 BR, the SER was one in the entire range of separation, while at the 600 and 1200 BR, SER was zero in the entire range of separation (except starting 2 to 3mm).

All the discussed results for SER vs Distance for IRWC can be seen in graph shown in Fig.7.

Fig 7. SER vs Distance graph for IRWC for baudrates between 600 to 57600.

CONCLUSION

This paper investigates a bidirectional hybrid OWC system for indoor networks, in which VLC was employed as downlink and IRWC as uplink. Results of the proposed OWC system indicates the variation SER with respect to separation between transmitter and receiver at different BRs. The SER increases with increasing separation at same BR or with increasing BR at same separation. The SER also increases due to saturation of PD. the saturation point (in separation) at different BRs are not same. In this research, the best SER vs distance range were obtained at BR 1200 and below 1200 for VLC and IRWC.

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